

Social Stigma of Single University Mothers

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to analyze the capacity of agency and the reflexivity that unmarried university mothers have about the stigmas that surround their motherhood are built in the Faculty of Chemical Science of the Autonomous University of San Luis Potosi (UASLP). This investigation is qualitative in nature. The methodology of life anecdotes through semi-structured individual interviews was used. It took place from February to May in the year 2014; the life anecdotes of 8 students with bachelors in the Faculty of Chemical Science were collected and analyzed; as well as 14 in depth interviews with professors, administrative and staff members. Parting from experience and reflection, they try to establish actions that in some cases, allows them to reach a level of autonomy to restate the stigmas, through lacking efforts of collective work and of elaborated ideas in respect to their sexual and reproductive rights that are directed about more structured demands. It is essential that young women organize themselves as a collective to demand their rights as mothers and students in the area of exact sciences and technologies. Likewise, the UASLP must assume the responsibility of generating changes in the stigmas, as well as, of supporting the permanence of the single mothers in the university.

Keywords: University, Single mothers, Social stigma, Agency, Students, Gender.

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1. Introduction

Goffman (1963/2010) [1] indicates that stigmas are conjured because of situations where the person does not experience complete social acceptance by being discredited due to his conditions, which are considered disadvantages. He explains that stigma appears when the person and his attribute (real identity); do not relate them self to what is socially accepted (virtual identity). In a determined context, this can cause social relations to be at an unequal condition in reference others, and therefore cause stigmatization.

In the decade of the seventies of the twentieth century, women who were mothers without having a husband at their side, suffered from a serious social rejection that was justified mainly because they had failed to comply with the moral norms that governed their sexuality (Arbiza, 1978) [2]. Currently, it is likely that young single mothers represent lower social exclusion as response to the incompliance's of maternity norms. These norms establish that there must be a family nucleus. This criterion is currently being modified, and now it seems that the moment in which they are mothers and the social space they belong to become mothers, are the key criteria to stigmatize them, such as the case of the participants of this study. They are young single mothers of the university *alumni* who, under determining social elements, are considered to not value maternity.

In general, the stigma implies that the stigmatized person experiments with social devaluation, transforming it into a part of their social identity (Goffman, 1963/2010) [1]. Scott (1999) [3] proposed to the agency as the ability of people to try to build an identity. The individual can generate resources to deal with the stigma however, and this is known as the capacity of agency.

The agency allows people to modify social aspects in limited situations, by using strategies that allows reflexive levels and actions to take place, and thus the development of resources to remove the stigmas. In this way, people are able to have the agency to maintain stigmas at a distance, to question and/or to appropriate them as part of their lives. Stigmatized individuals might also develop an agency to not assume their stigmas as determinants, restricting them like the control that the stigmas could hold over them.

Therefore, flexibility plays a fundamental role, and has been defined by Garfinkel as:

“(…) the capacity for individuals to recognize, demonstrate and make visible the racial characteristics of their concrete practices, without implying a consciousness nor permanent attention to this dimension” (Garfinkel, 1967, p. 247) [4].

On the other hand, Giddens establishes reflexivity like:

“(…) the capacity for the individuals as for the institutions of the social systems, to proceed in a continuous process to self-regulate using a critical distance” (Giddens 1984, 1990, 247) [5].

In the same way, Van Zanten (2007, p.249) [6] identifies reflexivity as: “(…) an adaptation of a position that is distant, informed, strategic and politically conscious in reference to their social experience”. These conceptualizations of the reflexivity are characterized by establishing that a person can have a critical position toward himself and the society, and as Van Zanten (2007) [6] implies, a political standpoint as well.

In respect to the relationship between reflexivity with the capacity of agency, Caetano (2014) [7] conceptualizes the re-flexibility as the capacity of a person to reflect on who they are without considering their social circumstances. He states that Beck Giddens and Lash place the concept of re-flexibility as a central element in the analysis of social change, although, Caetano (2014) [7] concludes that re-flexibility should not only be analyzed in relationship with social change, but also in the effects on individual agency.

The objective of this paper is to analyze the capacity of agency and the reflexivity that unmarried university mothers have about the stigmas that surround their motherhood are built in the context of the Faculty of Chemical Science of the Autonomous University of San Luis Potosi (UASLP)², Mexico.

² The Autonomous University of San Luis Potosi is the biggest, oldest and most recognized University of the State of San Luis Potosi, Mexico. The imaginary of the university student that is configured in the university is for them not to be a parent and for them to be full time students. Therefore there is not a daycare service for

The way students begin to represent social consequences of being single mothers and university students, while being conscious of their position is also analyzed. They begin to reflect and take actions that allow them to assume a level of autonomy towards stigmas. All of the above will be considered within a framework that handles tensions between these young ladies and the social and institutional system, and the process in which their university maternal identity becomes conformed. Given the theoretical inexistence of a definition of the university maternal identity, for this investigation was proposed to define it as:

“the social and subjective aspects that are constructed based on the way life is lived and recognized as mothers, by being students within the university systems. In specific the single mothers.” (Huerta, 2015, 91) [8].

At the beginning it was considered to work with the stigma of the single mother, but it resulted that in the specific context of the Faculty of Chemical Science, several stigmas that are manifested about these young girls must be considered. Therefore, it was decided to focus on the plural and speak about the stigmas of single mothers, in order to understand how, within the context of exact science and technology, specific stigmas are constructed based on these ladies. The research focus does not allow knowing if this phenomenon is presented in other institutions, or faculties of the UASLP, or even in other faculties of chemical science of different Autonomous Universities of Mexico.

1.1 This paper intend to answer the research questions

What are the stigmas that are built on young single university mothers in the Faculty of Chemical Sciences of the UASLP?

In what way do the young single university mothers exercise the capacity of agency and reflexivity with respect to the stigmas that form over them in the Faculty of Chemical Sciences of the UASLP?

the children of the students that attend the university nor is there an appropriate space for the girls to breast feed their children. On the other hand, after the child's birth they are only allowed 25% of absences, the same that is allowed under any other health leaves.

2. Methods

This investigation is qualitative in nature. The methodology of life anecdotes through semi-structured individual interviews was used. From February to May in the year 2014, life anecdotes of 8 students with bachelors in the Faculty of Chemical Science of the Autonomous University of San Luis Potosi were collected and analyzed. The names of the young ladies have been changed to keep them confidential. Also a contentment form was used for each participant for the use of this investigation about the information provided in the interviews. In order to understand the structural factors, 14 in depth interviews with professors, administrative and staff members of UASLP, were conducted, especially in the Faculty of Chemical Science. In order to work with this group, a guide of questions for the in-depth interviews was elaborated.

The selection criteria of the population sample were: for the participants to be between 18 and 29 years of age, registered as regular or irregular students in one of the majors of the Faculty of Chemical Science, single mothers without being legally married and to have this marital status at the moment of the interviews. Participants were partially or completely economically dependent of a family and social net. They also had to be living with their offspring.

In order to include diverse partner agreement, and in this way, extend the population diversification, the criteria of a nonexistent marriage contract was established. In the selection of the population sample was considered young women that have lived or are living in free union with the father of their child or children or with another partner, young ladies that have never co-lived with the father of their child or children and live independently from their parents or ladies that remain living with their family of origin.

As the percentage of students in the different majors of the Faculty of Chemical Science of UASLP was analyzed, results showed that in these educative spaces there is a vast feminine population represented, making up 56% of the total population of the major in the school cycle 2012-2013. This information drew our attention, because this Faculty hosts majors that belong to the area of knowledge of exact science and technology and traditionally do not have a large female population. This is the case in the Faculty of Science, where in the same school cycle, female students were up to 30% of the total students registered, but only 21% of the

Engineering Faculty is female (UASLP, 2012) [9].

The majors in the Faculty of Science have the following composition of gender domination in their enrolment³: Chemical Engineering (mixed), Bioprocessing Engineering (mixed), Food Engineering (female), Bachelors in Chemistry (mixed), Bachelors in Pharmaceutical Chemistry (female). Our other reasons for deciding to work with the Faculty of Chemical Science of UASLP included the high normative level that is demanded of their students: a full-time student dedication to their studies, due to the hours of laboratory practice. The Faculty of Chemical Science also has the most majors of any other Faculty at the university.

2.1 Data analysis

All the interviews were recorded, transcribed and codified. An analysis of conceptual level was carried out in the program ATLAS.ti., version 7.1.8. Content analysis methodology was used for the life anecdotes of each participant, as well as for the professor and staff interviews carried out.

The chosen methodology of life anecdotes is a modality of the methodology of life history; Jorge Aceves (2014) [11], identifies that oral history is focused on the total experience of the subjects, while a life anecdote is characterized by the search for answers based on a specific topic or a part of the subject's life.

The life anecdote methodology allows exploring social identity, through the triangulation of narration with other contextualized information, so we can understand how narrated experience has influenced the subject's identity (Bolívar, 2016) [12].

The analysis of life anecdotes can be carried out in relation with two logics: intra-case, which consists of a deep analysis of each story told (singular logic), and a transversal logic (inter-case) where all the life stories are analyzed based

on the central idea of the analytical topics established in advanced, as well as with those that arise in the analysis process (Cornejo, 2018) [13]. Both logics were used in this investigation.

It is worth mentioning that none of the participants present re-signification of all the types of stigma that were detected in this study. In general, they stay away from the majority of the stigmas and the ways their lives are interpreted all vary in specific aspects, and the way that they interpret their lives also vary. This supports the idea that although there might be similar points in reference to identity, the information is not homogenous.

3. Results

3.1 University single mothers: Eluding the stigmas of abortion and suicide

University single mothers are modifying the stigma that establishes maternity as a reason for women to retreat partially or completely to the private realm. These ladies can reconstruct the stereotype that tries to ratify the exclusion of mothers in the areas of exact science and technology and establish their children as the main justification and the impulse for their entrance and continuance in the university, even with low conditions that limit their possibilities to raise their children. The prior contradicts the information exposed by Calvario and Ravelo (1996) [14], who, in an investigation with Mexican universities reflecting on unexpected pregnancies, identified that in these cases abortion was used as an option due to the obstacle that maternity represented in their professional development: due to time, money, and psychological preparation that motherhood demands as well as the responsibilities that such condition would necessitate. All of the above indicates that many young ladies in their stay in the university are making decisions about keeping or not keeping the pregnancy, a conflictive process into which, in cities like San Luis Potosí, moral and legal aspects are inserted. These aspects regulate the prohibition of abortion and are only permitted under legal circumstances such as; rape, life threatening situations or unconsented artificial insemination. Abortion is not legal in San Luis Potosí if there are genetic or congenital alterations in the fetus (GIRE, 2015) [15].

Under this frame, it is important to consider the social context that establishes more or less agency over the configuration of the university maternal

³ The educational facilities are classified as males, females and mixed, depending on the percentage that is represented for each gender, in function to the following range of percentage: if more than 60% of their population is female, it is considered a female facility. If it is between 40% and 60% the faculty is considered mixed. If it is less than 40% the faculty is male. (Buquet, et al, 2006) [10].

identity. On the other hand, university students who become single mothers such as the ones that have an abortion – legal or illegally -, represent a challenge to the established postures that allow the creation of a sense of the interruption or continuance of the pregnancy. This this is implied in both cases, as a key aspect in the decisions, is the importance of acquiring and concluding their university studies.

One of the characteristics of the population of study is that the majority of the participants became mothers while they were university students; there is a variety in respect of the predominance and concentration of the studies done on teenage pregnancy in Mexico. This generates strong questioning in reference to the ladies that have diverse judgments that are generated based on ambiguous representations, since the lack of pregnancy prevention is still discussed, due to the education received and counting with the support provided by the university through the programs carried out based on sexual education. On the other hand, in gender logic in reference to maternity, these women are receiving higher social credit, when compared to those who decide to abort. This is how the student dynamics are established in reference to unexpected maternity, generating new narratives in reference to single mothers.

It's just...I have never been in favor or against abortion. Against because I do not think it is fair that because: it was an accident! Now I will have to do those types of thing. Because at our age, and more at our age, I think that when a person is under 18, it is due to ignorance or because they were not careful. But this does not happen at our age, because we are mature and we know what can come about from being careless, we need to be careful. It isn't "oh no a mistake!" but we are more conscious and I don't think it is an option, I see it as something unfavorable at our age, because we are mature (LAURA P.8:127,202:202).

...I feel I am brave because others...and brave to have had my daughter, because many...well in high school, at different ages, you are not mature in high school as in the university, but I saw how some got pregnant and got an abortion and another girl killed herself, so it's like brave to do it and to carry the load, to confront the consequences of a distraction, I mean you

are brave to do that and to carry a load that is not that light because ... it's not that your child is a load but rather the school and life in general (SOFIA P1:160, 321:321).

The participants were asked about the option of abortion, and although it was not one of the central points of the investigation, it gains strength within the narratives of the ladies and it becomes a component for the analysis of the stigmas, because abortion is a relevant element of the configuration of the university maternal identity. The topic of abortion is inserted as evidence of knowledge, its diffusion and the actions that based on this element have been developed in the last years, this has not only allowed current wide debates and reflection, but it has also been converted into a right, although it has not been generalized in all the states of the country. This is where the capacity of notion of Amartya Sen (1995) [16] (liberty to express what you want to do about what people value), this is done in order to question: how much are the narratives that refer to abortion in the university stage based on the freedom of choice and how much is founded on the limitations of the legal and social framework?

Placing ladies that decide not to be mothers under unexpected circumstances as different, allows the ones that do decide to embrace motherhood to construct an identity based on pride, an act of bravery, and honor of their gender. By doing this, they reproduce the traditional commandments of motherhood. Additionally, educative levels, information and age are associated as conditional elements for considering abortion as an option. Therefore, single mothers that are positioned as university students would be seen as transgressors, with less of a right to interrupt a pregnancy. This would leave abortion as a justifiable action only in younger girls, who might consider this option based on their immaturity; thus, discrediting the possibility that an abortion could result from an informed decision and being based on our reproductive and sexual rights.

When confronting an unexpected pregnancy, if an abortion is chosen by the university student, it becomes highly stigmatized, basically representing the imminent immersion of motherhood as the legal and socially valid alternative for the university student.

Suicide is another aspect that is also included in the narratives based on the configuration of university maternal identity, due to the high rate

that is currently presented among young girls. In Mexico, suicide has become the second reason for death in people between the ages of 15 to 29 (INEGI, 2017)⁴ [17]. Although males have first place in reaching the suicidal purpose, it is the females that have the highest rate in suicide attempts, as well as in the suicidal rate in adolescents in México (Zamora, 2015) [19].

Single mothers have an identity that differentiates them from “other” women who decide to have an abortion, as for those that choose the more radical option of suicide. Single mothers hold testimony of life preservation, not only of the lives of their children but also their own lives, thus providing the elements used to stigmatize other girls that due to a personal decision or complex circumstances choose other options. So that their status acquisition is defined by not valuing social presence of those “other girls” and become the object (of being stigmatized as single mothers) and part (and relieve themselves of other stigmas such as those placed on girls that decide to have an abortion or that commit suicide) from judgments that establish the reproduction of traditional motherhood.

3.2 Contradictions in their existence in the university: The amazement

Within the Faculty of Chemical Science, it is common for single mothers to be questioned by their classmates as well as teachers in reference to the way that they are able to combine their mother and student role and in some cases as workers. It is therefore possible for them to be identified by having greater academic problems, which can increase the stigma assigned to them due to absences, late arrivals, and difficulties working in teams. How they keep up with all the work becomes a common question and it also becomes an aspect that receives criticism in respect to their abilities and possibilities to remain in the university, a situation that too many young women becomes bothersome.

At first it was uncomfortable because it wasn't very common (...) when, there weren't many girls with kids, or they were very few, and if they did the kids were

older, (...) so at the beginning it was like, oh boy so young, studying and with a daughter! And I: ya. (LETICIA P7:15, 37:37).

...they have a vision that by being a mother (it is) an obstacle, like some type of experiment to do things, including some people hear: you are a mother, and ask: how do you do it? And you study? It's like very impressive that you are studying. Well, ya, you can study and stuff, and How do you do it? And how is it? Because...they do not see the way t do it, they see it as a stepping stone... (FATIMA. P.5:100,153:153).

...how do I do it, how do I do it to take care of my child, in order to study, to do my homework, well, more women: how do you do it?! I do not have enough time and you do it and take care of a kid. And I say: I don't know myself, but I just have to do it, I can't leave school or my kid (MARCELA P.3:198, 355:355)

They are judged for being mothers at a time that apparently is not the adequate time, and in a space that is not pertinent for them to be present. Consequently, it becomes common to question their presence in majors of exact science and technology due to the face to face time spent (attendance to school, laboratory practices and team projects), and in the elaboration of afterschool homework; therefore carrying out these tasks as a single mother makes them a target of questioning their capacity and how they dared take this challenge, and to finish this task. For many young students, being exposed to these types of questions on a daily basis, and how they are able to develop a university identity, is quite bothersome because it questions their abilities as students and as mothers.

Goffman (1963/2010) [1] establishes that a person that is stigmatized is in a “discredited position” when she realizes that she is perceived differently by others. This becomes an obstacle for her social acceptance, due to the trait that discredits her becomes more important than other aspects of her as a person, consequently she is discriminated against in different ways. It is in these young girls that anger is an emotion that reflects the attention that is established by their presence in the university, because they become part of a population that generates questioning. And it is unexplainable the fact that they remain in school and make the school requirements. Considering

⁴ “In 2011, 43% of the cases of suicide in Mexico were presented in young population (15-19 years of age) the age group most effected is the one of 20 to 24 years of age (16% of the total number of cases), followed by the group of 15-19 years of age (15%of the total cases)” (Instituto Mexicano de la Juventud, 2014, 35) [18].

the dynamics of the system the “How do you do it?” question can be a level of curiosity, by which several of these ladies are not bothered, but other times it can become irritating because they have to provide explanations that imply a justification of why they transgress their condition of inequality.

The identity of these young ladies is configuring with the tension between the uncertainty that the context generates in reference to their school requirements and the annoyance that this might represent. The annoyances are seen from an isolated posture without the development of concrete actions under a more profound understanding of laws and social programs that would allow better social integration. Although, if they generate an interest to carry out collective actions, they would go from individual incommodity to the creation of actions that would allow them to be positioned like political actors with proposals and more structured demands in order to unmask the limitations.

On the other hand, single ladies are socially re-understood; if beforehand they fell under an immoral stigma because they had a child out of wedlock, now under the other motherhood identities of the university, such as those applied to pregnant girls who decide to have an abortion (whether from personal choice or due to medical conditions), the ones that decide to have their baby receive recognition for not interrupting their pregnancy. It must be considered, however, situations that are not dealt with in this representation; such as if abortion is truly a feasible option or if having the baby is imposed on them by their family or their romantic partner or even due to the moral precepts that fall on them about their socialization.

The ideal of the university student is represented by a person who knows how to plan his future; a characteristic acquired while at the university, and is expected to be developed in the intermediate years. Therefore, the stigma can become greatly marked towards the young university women who get pregnant and become single mothers in an unforeseen way, question the orientation function of the university, and generate a relationship of tension with the institution. These girls do not comply with the social expectations of entering motherhood until their university education is culminated. By incorporating themselves in a university they begin to generate modifications to a part of their stigmatized identity and influence

new institutional discourses in reference to the university students.

...at times I would like to be young, in order to understand students... that's why one used to believe in the customs that our parents transmitted to us but now I don't know... I do not know what happens (...) I do not remember if when I was studying if I had classmates in that situation, I would say that in those times we did not have the information about preservatives, and those of my generation we accepted as law what our mothers used to say, to be careful, to take care of ourselves, to not get pregnant, the idea that school comes first. I see kids now a days have a lot of information, but that information makes them to be overconfident and girls believe that it won't happen to them, that a pregnancy is not possible because they will be careful, and it turns out that before they realize it they are in that situation. There are two or three cases in the present that decide to have an abortion. I know that between them they tell each other and they go and have an abortion. Here in the faculty there was a specific extraordinary case, where girls have miscarriages due to possible threats, and this leaves signs... we do not know. And others that for some reason decide to confront the situation, I do not know if this decision is made consciously or unconsciously, or they just might not have another choice ... (CORDINATOR FCQ P FCQ P<3:38, 16:16).

...it's been several years. A boy arrived and said: -teacher I am very anguished, I got my girlfriend pregnant, and she is studying law-. The boy was in his second year of his major, or something like that. -I do not want to have it, she says she will have an abortion. And I told her to please not, to not have an abortion, that I can drop out of school, and that I would take care of it, for her not to worry that I would take care of things but for her not to have an abortion. The boy was truly concerned. This was surely due to the principles that the boy had been installed, to the value given to life, right? And I finally asked him what had happened and he told me that she had not paid attention to him and ended up doing what she wanted. This represented a heavy load on his conscious,

and she is fine with it, she was able to do it and she did not care (the last phrase was stressed). Knowing that the father of the child supported her, in other cases this is not present. I believe that this is becoming common in females, where girls are taking on different characteristics, believing they are equals, the famous feminism. They got rid of “the macho” ideas, and say “no” and the girls are taking it out on the poor men, because men will still be men, and they want to rebel, and are trying to carry everything. The “macho” man will keep being the “macho” man and they will continue with their feminism and will try to take on both roles and are realizing that it is a very difficult task. That is thinking of those girls that get pregnant and decide to have the baby, they have double responsibility, right? (...) Character, character, they are strong woman. They are able to say yes to life besides...they are admirable, of course, admirable (PROFESSOR FCQ P.<10:41, 24:24).

Currently, students’ sexual lives interrupt gender identity, and have become, in a way, in a situation not understood from an institutional standpoint. It is recognized that young people today look to establish gender equality, although, within the same university it is perceived that some pretensions are ambiguous, since in several situations the relationships between males and females are established, under a patriarchal structure, where professors are witnesses of the disadvantages that such social dynamics have over female students.

Within the university, there is a gender difference that is assumed ambiguously - and at the same time changing and natural - and is not established as sexual and reproductive rights. The educative context is not considered as a priority to generate cultural modifications towards respect, as well as, the generational gap (between university personal and students) as a justification that limits the development of actions to prevent and assist these situations.

There are contradictions in the way the university students are represented as subjects who deserve sexual and reproductive health services, and in turn as transgressors of the socially established in terms of sexual behavior. It is fundamental that as far as young voices are concerned, the cultural aspects that are constructing their identity can be

identified, as well as recuperate what Butler identifies as “the way we construct ourselves”, from approaching identity parting from “the experiences and actions” that these young single mothers carry out in the university context.

Due to the situation, it is fundamental to transform university students into active public debaters that allow reflexive daily life work considering the codes in relation to gender that are established within the university, and that in part, could be contributing to the reproduction of unequal relationships between genders.

On the other hand, alternating maternity with their student tasks amplifies situations in which they are identified with it puts them in a higher position since it generates admiration. This way they gain a sense of identity that distinguishes them in a positive way from the rest of their classmates; they start living situations in which the ways they carry out their university life is recognized, it strengthens them and becomes an essential part of their identity as university single mothers.

And now, with all my classmates, they tell me, they congratulate me, because they tell me, that I have guts...sorry ... (cries) now most people congratulate me, they say – congratulations because it is a great responsibility to be a mother and to be a student, its very hard. - because I have classmates that are from out of town, and here they have the responsibility of house chores and school tasks, and for them it is very difficult. And they say: -now that you are a mom, you work and school. - they tell me that I surprise them and that I am an example to follow. And stuff like this. (KARLA P4:44, 62:62).

...my friends tell me: - it’s like I admire you because even if you do not believe it you are a very strong woman- and I can’t believe it. Right? - Why not, not many like you are able to stand out, and stuff like that, and you are here, your son and all of that. And I say: - the truth is that I do feel a bit strong, and yes I have lived things that others have not at my age. But these are the things that make me continue ...a lot...many people say, you know I couldn’t the truth is that, it’s cool that you look for strength and see it naturally. I say, well yes, life teaches you to see it naturally, because we do not want to be responsible, you have to see things more

naturally, then it takes you to normality and not be embarrassed, it's just that to say that I have a son, so what, and they say, well in reality you deal with it well I admire you, I do not know how much and I say, no well thank-you, I do my best. (LAURA P8:250, 409:409)

Conforming to a maternal university identity, can create a division in the reality that they knew as students before becoming single mothers. This implies what Laura presents as “making it normal”, it's to say, considering it more convenient to intend to configure a maternal university identity, that won't fall into polarities, like what happens when it positions itself as inadequate, nor positioning as a population that openly changes the system through its maternity; therefore, in their daily lives, some of these young ladies look for intermediations that allow them to have a better social integration.

These ladies identify in their stories, the admiration by some people within the institution, which represents some contradictions about the way they are represented. That is to say, that implied in the surprise about their permanence in the university is the other students' recognition that the system does not provide much help to make this possible; it is the recognition of the lack of solidarity towards these ladies. The admiration disguises the uncertainty that is generated due to their fragile academic position and can contribute to the creation of the stereotyping of the admired motherhood, but now due to the idea of sacrificial living, as a way to receive credit for her presence in public space. The isolated admiration of concrete actions hides and perpetuates institutional and social indifference towards these women; based on this idea, they go through a relationship of tension between the efforts made by these ladies in order to be included in the university, and the surprise that results from staying in a system in which they are made invisible. The admiration is evidence of their actions in solitary, and it highlights the representation of individual conflict and not of institutional or social responsibility.

David Madrigal (2014) [20] explains that when there are conflicts and tense situations that have been presented for a long period of time, this can produce a “non-conflict” process; in which a “harmony” under tension, where the interactions are characterized by a non-visible violence, and an

inequality of power is viewed⁵. In the case of these young women, the combination of astonishment and the institutional incomprehension of their presence in the university, develop non-conflictive relationships which result in social exclusion. On the other hand, the approval that these women receive in the expressions of admiration (without problematizing more than the annoyance that may be occasioned), lead them to insert themselves in borderline spaces, in part, due to the apparent benefit that they obtain from being visible and recognized socially based on the admiration. This is a non-conflict situation where gender becomes a transversal support for the integration of the university maternal identity under situations that naturalize a light form of violence, and that strengthens the stereotypes of maternity in public spaces. All of this underlies an acceptance on behalf of the young girls that contribute to disguising their own discrimination.

4. Conclusions

Young single mothers on their way through the university in the area of exact science and technology establish a process of re-significance of several of the stigmas that are manifested in reference to their presence in this context. It must be made clear that it is common for the participants to have an ambiguous agency; in such a way that several aspects legitimize their stigma and in others they carry out efforts in order to not be included in the stigmatized identity.

The maternal identity of university students, who are single mothers, is a complex social process due to the ambiguities that are presented in relation to the context, as well as to the variations that these women establish about the way they confront their reality inside and outside the university. In this dynamic they are building, in a particular way, autonomous areas configure identity modifications, which influence the way that they are represented socially. In this view, the presence of single mothers that are university students in areas of exact sciences and technology, has made way for the manifestation of a series of stigmas. As they recognize this position, they establish reflections and actions that

⁵ Madrigal addresses the no conflict from a socio-atmosphere frame, he explains it as a way in which the conflict is naturalized due to economic interests of the parts, although, there is always greater control of one group over another.

allow them to configure a maternal identity that transcends some odd ends of these stigmas, a conflictive process of which a concrete identity is not defined or complete. This is established by Butler (2007) [21] as “gender disorder”, originating when the identity generates modifications in the norm identities, thus creating diverse identities that cannot be generalized, since they are related with the political and cultural spaces where they take place.

The construction of the maternal identity of the university student is established in a process that integrates agencies in reference to the social credit, exclusion, control and demands on this identity. When these young girls challenge the stigmas that are placed on them in the university, they start constructing their identity among contradictions, uncertainties, and challenges.

They must build a process in which they assume in a non-permanent way to have capacities to stay in the institution. This posture has an impact on the stigmas that are developed on them in this context of high educational demand. Parting from experience and reflection, they try to establish actions that in some cases, allows them to reach a level of autonomy to restate the stigmas, through lacking efforts of collective work and of elaborated ideas in respect to their sexual and reproductive rights that are directed about more structured demands.

The participants present diverse ways of reflection. A defensive level and that of annoyance is related with the irritation in reference to the stigmas regarding the judgments that are made about their morality or their capacity to continue in the university. On the other hand, they are able to reach a critical agency that they use in order to justify their stay in the university, in which it is established that the child and the status that they obtain in becoming mothers are the main reasons for being a university student.

Their reflections are constructed in reference to their condition, and become fundamental points of knowledge of their capacity of agency toward the single mother stigma. Carrying out the agency to mean different things allows them to broaden their margin of action within their social scenery. In all the narratives these young women assert that it depends on themselves and on their focus to change the stigma. Greatly valued resources manifest the way that they carry out their sexual and reproductive rights (although not precisely under those terms). Yet, in a large amount they do

not consider as fundamental the role that the institution and its members might have to generate change on the stigmas, even though this would allow transcending the isolated actions into individual that they present in their university lives.

Their reflection processes allow them to have a greater agency on what they are, where they want to be and in what way. In many cases it is also a reflection of concrete actions that transcend the reflection and challenge of not being identified as it stipulates socially.

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